

INDIA'S PRESS AND MEDIA LIBERTY

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INTRODUCTION

Ever since 1880s, India has had a thriving and robust media. Television, radio, cinema, newspapers, magazines, and Internet-based Websites/portals are among the several sorts of mass media communications in India. However, according to the Press Freedom Index, India scored 142nd out of 180 nations in 2020, that is said to be attributed to Prime Minister Narendra Modi's Bharatiya Janata Party and its Hindutva adherents imposing increased influence over the media. Even as its sympathizers threaten outlets and particular reporters, the government has initiated punitive charges against media that contradict its judgments. In addition, according to a study released in 2021 by Freedom House, intimidation of journalists intensified under Modi's leadership.

In any democratic society, press freedom is a crucial fundamental right. It is simply an amplification of a person's right to free speech and expression. People must generate their own beliefs and make their own evaluations in an open society. As a result, the press plays a crucial role in disseminating information to the public.

WHAT IS FREEDOM OF PRESS & MEDIA?

The notion that interaction and interpretation through different media, including written and electronic media, especially published information, should be acknowledged a right to be exercised freely is known as freedom of the press or freedom of the media. Such liberty means the exclusion of state involvement; its maintenance may be sought through a constitution or other legal safeguards.

THE MANDATE FOR PRESS & MEDIA FREEDOM

The press is a medium for disseminating knowledge and vital information about events, developments, and occurrences of national interest to the entire nation, and thus its fair and transparent action serves as the backbone of civil society, capable of crucial and objective

thinking and forming informed opinions about the country and government after carefully evaluating the realities of the situation.

PRESS & MEDIA FREEDOM IN PRE-INDEPENDENCE ERA

The Vernacular Press Act, the Censorship of Press Act, 1799, and the Indian Press Act, 1910 all safeguarded the British Indian press, while the Licensing Regulations, 1823, the Licensing Act, 1857, and the Registration Act, 1867 monitored the media organisations and news outlets. The British administration in India implemented a system of laws and regulations to prevent the spread of misinformation, media manipulation, and misinformation across the Indian subcontinent.

Prior to the 1857 Indian Rebellion, the press was deeply invested in the independence movement and coverage of demonstrations, prompting the government to engage in self-censorship of press freedom.

Subsequently, the government implemented four new laws that put forth a comprehensive set of guidelines for media companies. Newspapers (Incitement to Offenses) Act 1908, Prevention of Seditious Meetings Act 1911, Indian Press Act 1910, Criminal Law Amendment Act 1908, and Secrets Act 1903 were among several.

In 1919, the government enacted the Rowlatt Act, which allowed the government to hold persons engaging in anti-government activities indefinitely without charge or trial. The Act was also intended to limit writing, speech, and movements that took place in the context of civil disobedience policies.

Following the Quit India Movement in 1942, the press was told not to report on political parties. Following that, the All-India Newspaper Editors' Conference produced a government directive declaring that publications should exercise prudence and avoid from writing on the Quit India Movement.

FREEDOM OF PRESS AND MEDIA AT PRESENT

Since the nation's founding, the media has relentlessly promoted the leaders' personality cult. It covered the leader's activities, including political campaigns, and frequently included "advertisements" for ruling parties on radio, television, and newspaper display advertising. Local media within India sometimes only publishes news that benefits the government, while

news that covers the country's economic and political difficulties, or critiques of the government, receive government-issued warnings.

In 2017, three journalists were slain in the course of their work. Gauri Lankesh, a proponent of secularism and a critic of right-wing movements, was shot dead outside her home, according to Reporters without Borders. Lankesh was assassinated by a member of a Hindu nationalist gang. Several journalists, notably Sagarika Ghose and Ravish Kumar, have claimed that they were harassed, intimidated, and threatened with murder or rape because they were hostile of the Bharatiya Janata Party administration.

To prevent peace and order from breaking down in India, the government of India limited media coverage of Citizenship Amendment Act demonstrations in 2019. Some of the coverage on CAA demonstrations was "promotion of anti-national ideas," according to the federal authorities and India's Prime Minister.

Since August 2019, when Article 370 of the Indian Constitution, which granted Jammu & Kashmir special status, was repealed, Kashmiri journalists have been subjected to a pattern of intimidation and monitoring. Journalists have been harassed, roughed up, and arrested under the 1967 Unlawful Activities (Prevention) Act.

The Press Council of India, a government-owned organisation, said that censorship of mass media by government authorities, particularly state police, is negative, citing "intimidation" of journalists and "curtailment" of press freedom as examples. Authorities have purportedly accused the country's news outlets and its affiliated journalists with sedition and criminal prosecution.

The Indian government issued warnings against international media such as The New York Times, The Guardian, Al Jazeera, The Washington Post, Time Magazine, The Economist, BBC, and Huffington Post in 2020 or before for adversely depicting India's image.

FREEDOM OF PRESS DURING COVID-19 TIMES

Reporters and other opposing voices in India are increasingly fearful of persecution at a time when information is crucial and journalists are risking their lives on the front lines to convey crucial stories. Journalist persecution is not restricted to one political party; similar tactics are used throughout the political spectrum. The Maharashtra police have arrested Rahul Zori, a

reporter for TV9 Marathi, for reporting on anomalies at migrant assistance camps in Dhule, Maharashtra, according to NewsLaundry.

Journalists throughout India are being charged with sedition and called to police stations for reporting on the government's handling of the coronavirus epidemic, which has been in effect since March 24. At least six journalists have been charged in Himachal Pradesh with 10 FIRs for reporting on India's immigration issue and the lack of food delivery in the area. The migratory issue is threatening to become as serious as the epidemic.

At least 667 people have died as a result of India's hastily declared lockdown, according to research by Thejesh GN, Kanika Sharma, Krushna, and Aman, for causes ranging from malnutrition to police violence to suicides and accidents.

The BJP-led cabinet has petitioned the Supreme Court to prevent the disclosure of any COVID-19 data that has not been cleared by them. The motion was dismissed, but the court ordered the media to "*refer to and report the official account of the happenings.*"

In a recent Supreme Court hearing, it was declared that "free citizens cannot exist when the news media is shackled to conform to one perspective and all but one FIR against Republic TV editor-in-chief Arnab Goswami was annulled.

The site immediately removed a New Indian Express piece questioning the sudden lack of officials from the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) from government press conferences and the federal government's unwillingness to provide data.

Over 4,600 individuals have signed a declaration opposing the government's actions, including former Supreme Court justices, chiefs of naval staff, professors, artists, actors, and authors.

ARTICLE 19 AND FREEDOM OF PRESS

Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution, which guarantees freedom of speech and expression under Part III, includes a provision for press freedom (fundamental rights).

Freedom to spread & receive information

The major distinction between press freedom and individual freedom of speech is that a person cannot interact with the masses on his own, but a press may do so through its publications on various mediums such as print, radio, and electronic media. As a result, the freedom to disseminate information is an integral aspect of journalistic freedom. If the press is not supplied with information, it will be unable to provide knowledge to the public, and so the right to freedom of speech will be rendered useless since there would be no access to information on which anything may be stated.

Freedom to report court proceedings and to attend and report legislative proceedings

The freedom to publish a kosher report of parliamentary sessions is guaranteed under Article 361 of the Constitution. The sole restriction on this liberty is that such disclosures must not be made with a malicious motive. The live broadcasting of parliamentary events has been essential in recent years. In *Saroj Iyer v Maharashtra Medical (Council) of Indian Medicine*, the Supreme Court decided that even if it is against quasi-judicial bodies, the freedom to print truthful descriptions of court procedures seen exists.

Freedom to criticize

Individuals and the press both have the right to criticise the government, its officials, policies, acts, laws, and remarks, among other things. The press, on the other hand, cannot misuse this privilege by inciting the population to oppose the government.

Reasonable Restrictions on Freedom of Press

This limitation would apply to any type of speech or expression that jeopardises the state's sovereignty or integrity. The right to freedom of speech and expression cannot be used as a weapon against a country's sovereignty or integrity.

The Supreme Court declared in *State of Bihar v Shailabala Devi* that any speech made by any individual (citizen or non-citizen) that encourages individuals to commit crimes like as dacoity, murder, robbery, and so on is without a doubt a threat to the state's security. As a result, freedom of expression cannot be utilised in a way that impedes the state's security in any way.

Though freedom of speech and expression is important, it cannot be used to overturn a court's decision. No one is authorised to use any speech, sign, or gesture to expose a person to hatred, ridicule, or contempt.

Inciting an offence via freedom of speech and expression would be deemed a danger to public order.

The word "public order" has a broad definition that encompasses a wide range of behaviours that may jeopardise the state's security. The word "public order" might be interpreted as "no insurrections, riots, or disturbances to public peace," according to the Court as held in *Madhu Limaye v Sub Divisional Magistrate Monghyr SC*.

JUDICIAL PRECEDENTS

In Romesh Thapper v. State of Madras,

A legislation prohibiting the admission and distribution of journals in a state was found to be unconstitutional. The Court found that there is no question that freedom of speech and expression includes freedom of idea dissemination, and that this freedom is guaranteed by freedom of circulation.

In D.C. Saxena (Dr.) v. Chief Justice of India,

The Court held that, No one else has the authority to accuse a judge of misbehaviour, bias, or incompetence, according to the Supreme Court. The goal of such a safeguard is to guarantee

the independence of the judiciary, so that judges can make decisions without fear or favour, since the courts were established by the Constitution for the purpose of dispensing justice.

In Bennet Colman and Co. v. Union Of India,

The constitutional legitimacy of the News Print Control Order, which set the maximum number of pages (ten) that a newspaper may publish, was challenged as a violation of Article 19 (1)(a) and Article 14 of the constitution. The Supreme Court rejected this argument and upheld the "impact" standard for determining whether the challenged law's "impact" is to abridge a fundamental right.

CONCLUSION

In 1919, the government enacted the Rowlatt Act, which allowed the government to hold persons engaging in anti-government activities indefinitely without charge or trial. The Act was also intended to limit writing, speech, and movements that took place in the context of civil disobedience policies. Though, without a question, we must provide the press sufficient independence in order to preserve democracy and not promote an informed populace in the country.

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